

THE IMPORTANCE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

The relevance of the article is explained by the fact that today information and communication technologies are an important basis for the development of the economy. The main directions of organizational and economic development during the transition to a post-industrial society were considered in the article. The role of information technologies in the development of the digital economy was revealed, and the measures to increase the rate of economic growth and innovative development of the society through the introduction of information technologies were described. We describe the measures to increase the rate of economic growth and the rate of innovative development of the society based on the introduction of information technologies.

Keywords: Digital economy, information and communication technologies, cloud technology, post-industrial, cloud infrastructure, infrastructure of information and communication technologies.

I. INTRODUCTION

The transition to a post-industrial society allowed information and communication technologies to become one of the main components of the development of a knowledge-based digital economy. The dynamic growth of the technical and economic characteristics of high-tech innovative products will help to significantly increase the computing power and intellectual potential of products, and to quickly change outdated standards and technological platforms of information and communication systems and networks. At the same time, the operation of ultra-high-speed networks, mobile devices and information systems is aimed at improving the quality of multimedia content and a wide range of services for the population.

Today, the new types of products and services provided by global innovation networks have the power to manage all stages of the life cycle. The increase in demand for new and modified types of high-tech products and services is associated with the

rapid development of information and communication technologies and their rapid obsolescence, resulting in a shortening of the life cycle.[1]

II. The role of cloud technologies in the digital economy

The spread of cloud technologies, the exponential growth of data volumes, significant changes in the architecture and organization of computing systems, in our opinion, will lead to changes in the business model and infrastructure solutions in most industries, and the emergence of breakthrough innovations. in the process of developing the enterprise development strategy and the digital economy in general.[2] In this regard, it should be noted that currently the potential for prospective development of information and communication technologies is significantly increasing based on: the transition to the knowledge economy, which is one of the main factors of the development of the digital economy; creation of information and communication technologies and increase of production centers of new types of products and services; development of electronic government and socially important services for the population; cooperation of innovative business entities with universities, production laboratories, technology parks, business incubators, which allows to create radically new types of products and services; development of electronic business and formation of new legal and technological mechanisms of electronic transactions. it allows to create radically new types of products and services; development of electronic business and formation of new legal and technological mechanisms of electronic transactions. it allows to create radically new types of products and services; development of electronic business and formation of new legal and technological mechanisms of electronic transactions.[3]

The organizational-economic factor of strengthening the role of information and communication technologies in ensuring the effective functioning of the state and municipal management system is one of the priority conditions for the development of the digital economy in our country today. In addition to the widespread use of social network technologies and advanced cloud infrastructure, which are used to solve complex analytical problems, special attention should be paid to the development of the IT outsourcing market, mobile devices and applications. Cloud solutions, big data, mobile and social technologies encourage cross-development in these situations. In addition, due to the increase in the use of mobile devices, the activity of users on social networks is increasing.[4]

In the modern world, with the development of information technology and computer technology, it is no longer possible to imagine the activity of a successfully developing company without the use of information technology and automated systems, which are the main driving force today. By itself, an IT-automated enterprise can have a disruptive effect due to the lack of interoperability and integrity of the entire

system.[5] All this is primarily related to the global leap in the development of information technologies and systems, as a result of which the standardization of products does not correspond to technical standards. Therefore, the company implements current trends in the market of information technologies and systems. should monitor the effective flow of business processes, and appropriately respond to changes in the external business environment. The international economy is developing day by day and becoming more and more digital, that is, due to the development of digital technologies such as electronic payments, online shopping, crowdfunding, etc.[6,7] In this economy, the Internet and other networks, including social networks, facilitate the globalization of business and direct and indirect control over the behavior of firms, organizations, and individuals. related to the development of digital technologies such as crowdfunding and others. In this economy, the Internet and other networks, including social networks, facilitate the globalization of business and direct and indirect control over the behavior of firms, organizations, and individuals. related to the development of digital technologies such as crowdfunding and others. In this economy, the Internet and other networks, including social networks, facilitate the globalization of business and direct and indirect control over the behavior of firms, organizations, and individuals.[8,9]

III. Infrastructures Of Digital Economy And Information Technologies

"The digital economy is an economic activity in which the main factor of production is information in digital form, the use of large volumes of processing and analysis results in different production, technologies, equipment, storage, sales, goods and services compared to traditional forms of management. can significantly improve delivery efficiency.[10,11]

In the economy, especially in the service sector, information technology comes to the fore, because without it, it is impossible to improve quality and effectively manage business processes. However, information technologies have different effects on the economy depending on the purpose of their application. Information technologies aimed at meeting existing needs are usually not economically justified. Countries that have clearly defined the policy of introducing information technologies can calculate the results of this process, taking into account the material, financial and labor costs.[8,9,10]

Information technology policy planning process should be proportional to the country's economic development indicators. To date, some elements of the digital economy are already working well, such as e-government. In many countries, communications are gradually moving to an electronic platform, mass transfer of documents and communications to digital carriers is being carried out, and the use of electronic signatures is allowed. However, not all elements are being digitized so

successfully. In order to understand which elements are behind and which are advanced, it is necessary to have an idea of how to measure the level of development of the Digital Ecosystem in specific components and in the country as a whole.[8,9,10]

The world experience of the development of computer technologies and information resources shows that in recent years, their pace of development has significantly increased compared to the pace of development of the manufacturing sector. A high rate of information technology adoption promotes economic growth. The main characteristics of information technologies are as follows: expediency, the main goal of the introduction and implementation of certain information technologies is to reduce costs, increase profits, speed up and simplify the process of work. Each technology has certain components responsible for processing information and performing certain tasks. Components are arranged in a consistent hierarchical structure. and should interact with each other competently and without errors. Information technology makes sense if all its components interact with each other. None of its components can solve the problems that technology itself solves. Information technologies are rapidly developing and improving, new components are being added and structures are changing. The revolutionary impact of information and communication technologies affects people's way of life, education and work, business structures and state institutions, as well as the interaction between government and society.[7,8] ICT development is the most dynamic area of social production. it makes sense if all its components interact with each other. None of its components can solve the problems that technology itself solves. Information technologies are rapidly developing and improving, new components are being added and structures are changing. The revolutionary impact of information and communication technologies affects people's way of life, education and work, business structures and state institutions, as well as the interaction between government and society. ICT development is the most dynamic area of social production. it makes sense if all its components interact with each other. None of its components can solve the problems that technology itself solves.[9,10] Information technologies are rapidly developing and improving, new components are being added and structures are changing. The revolutionary impact of information and communication technologies affects people's way of life, education and work, business structures and state institutions, as well as the interaction between government and society. ICT development is the most dynamic area of social production. cannot solve the problems that zi solves. Information technologies are rapidly developing and improving, new components are being added and structures are changing. The revolutionary impact of information and communication technologies affects people's way of life, education and work, business structures and state institutions, as well as the interaction between government and

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Over the past decade, computers and software have developed so rapidly that their material base has improved, and with the emergence of new knowledge and technologies, they have found new forms and qualities. The main information technologies that affect the world economy include:

- Internet- this technology has solved the problem of information transmission, now it can be received anywhere and anytime.
- Email- is based on the use of the network by computers and allows receiving, storing and distributing information on the network;
- Audio mail- mail for sending voice messages;
- Computer conferencing and video conferencing- the use of new technologies to exchange information between group members helps to solve certain problems.
- Fax connection- this is a communication based on the use of a fax machine with the ability to encrypt the document at one end of the connection and reproduce its image at the other end;
- Interactive digital television is a massive multi-purpose interactivity that can satisfy the social order for a range of new services, including distance learning, telemedicine, shopping and more. Under the influence of information globalization, structural changes or shifts occur in the world economy that increase the interaction of the national economy.

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